

Genetic nature of leaf epicuticular wax (EW) content in rice

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Leaf EW content has been related to drought resistance in sorghum, wheat, barley, soybean, and maize. EW content in rice leaves increases cuticular resistance to transpiration, which may confer dehydration tolerance. We studied the genetic nature of EW content in rice leaves in 1988-89.

Leaf EW of phytotron-grown plants was extracted with chloroform, the chloroform evaporated off with N₂ gas, and EW reconstituted in 3 ml CCl₄. This solution was injected into a gas-liquid chromatograph (GLC). EW content in the solution of each sample was quantified by comparing total area under the three highest GLC peaks per unit leaf area extracted (Fig. 1). These three peaks, corresponding to C₂₉, C₃₃, and C₃₅ hydrocarbons, consistently accounted for almost all the leaf EW.

Eight parents with high or low leaf EW were crossed in all possible ways except

as reciprocals. The F₁ of the diallel set was analyzed by Griffing and Haymen's methods. Two F₂ populations were studied.

Upland parents IAC25, OS4, and IRAT13 had the highest EW levels. These cultivars belong to Glaszmann's isozyme group VI (japonica). General combining ability (GCA) effects were highly significant and specific combining ability (SCA) effects nonsignificant, indicating a predominance of additive genetic variation. Broad- (h^2_b) and

narrow-sense (h^2_n) heritability were 0.77 and 0.62, respectively. IAC25 and OS4 had the highest positive GCA.

Monomodal distributions were observed in both F₂ populations. In IAC25/Salumpikit (Fig. 2), the number of recombinants matching the EW level of either parent was low, implying polygenic inheritance. Broad-sense heritability was 0.36.

Predominance of additive genetic variation for EW content implies that selection to increase leaf EW would be effective. Low heritability and the difficulty in measuring the trait, however, are obstacles to increasing the EW level in improved rainfed lowland cultivars. An additional constraint is that the sources of high EW are upland cultivars, which are difficult to use in rainfed lowland breeding programs. ■

2. Distribution of leaf EW content in the F₂ population of IAC25/Salumpikit and the range, mean, and SE of the mean. Mean EW contents of P₁, P₂, and F₁ were 16.5, 5.9, and 10.5 mg/m², respectively.

Breeding methods

Evaluating S₁ family recurrent selection in a rice population

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Recurrent selection has been used to improve particular traits in breeding populations of cross-pollinating crops. Difficulties in artificial crossing, however, make it difficult to use in self-pollinating crops such as rice.

Genetic male sterility can facilitate crossing during the intermating phase of recurrent selection. We evaluated S₁ family recurrent selection in the composite population CP103 (IR38499) segregating for genetic male sterility. As the S₁ generation segregated for male sterility, we selected S₁-derived S₃ and S₄ lines, which were homozygous for male fertility.

In 1989 wet season (WS), 79 S₁ lines and 46 S₃ lines were grown. In 1990 dry season (DS), 62 S₁ and 34 S₄ lines were grown. S₁ lines were replicated twice and S₃ and S₄ lines four times each season. Agronomic and grain quality traits were measured on 12 hills/plot. Only plots not affected by rats and tungro were included in the analysis. IR36 could not be

1. Representative gas liquid chromatograms of high-wax IRAT13 and low-wax IR5. The numbers on top of each peak are retention time.

included in the 1990 DS analysis because of damage.

Means and ranges for the S₁ lines are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Lines comparable with or better than the best check occurred in both seasons, although this population had not undergone previous selection for yield.

In 1989 WS, correlations between S₁ and the corresponding S₃ lines were significant for all traits except adjusted yield. Yield of IR68 was reduced by typhoon damage.

In 1990 DS, correlations were significant for all traits except days to 50% flowering and percentage unfilled grains.

As S₁ lines are segregating for male sterility, and the amount of seed is limited, it is difficult to evaluate yield directly. Our study indicates that yield components and grain quality traits can be measured on fertile S₁ plants in small plots. These measurements appear to reflect differences observed in fertile S₁-derived S₃ or S₄ lines. This indicates S₁ selection could be used in a recurrent selection program to improve these traits. ■

Table 1. Ranges, means, and LSD for grain quality and agronomic traits of 46 S₁ lines with check means and correlation coefficients (r) between the S₁ and the corresponding S₃ generations. IRRI, 1989 WS.

Character	S ₁ lines		Checks		LSD (0.05)	r ^a
	Range	Mean	IR36	IR68		
Plant height (cm)	91-170	120	96	128	10.9	0.92**
Days to 50% flowering	91-125	105	89	103	7.3	0.68**
Brown rice length (mm)	6.0-7.4	6.7	6.7	7.9	0.41	0.82**
Brown rice shape (L/W)	2.35-3.60	3.07	3.45	3.70	0.31	0.90**
Gelatinization temp score	3.71-7.00	5.74	4.46	6.50	1.13	0.70**
Panicles/hill	10-20	15	20	13	5.5	0.49*
Spikelet no./panicle	92-206	151	120	131	46.5	0.77**
% unfilled grains	19-55	36	23	45	16.3	0.58**
100-grain weight (g)	2.18-3.16	2.56	2.35	3.02	0.28	0.60**
Adjusted yield (g/2.25m ²)	537-1414	965	848	749	452	0.26 ns

^aCorrelation between 26 pairs of S₁ and their derived S₃ lines. *, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Table 2. Ranges, means, and LSD for grain quality and agronomic traits of 32 S₁ lines with check means and correlation coefficients (r) between the S₁ and the corresponding S₄ generations. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Character	S ₁ lines		Check	LSD (0.05)	r ^a
	Range	Mean	IR36		
Plant height (cm)	84-150	108	109	10.1	0.68**
Days to 50% flowering	83-102	93	95	4.7	0.36 ns
Brown rice length (mm)	6.0-7.6	6.8	8.1	0.43	0.80**
Brown rice shape (L/W)	2.30-3.45	2.93	3.60	0.29	0.81**
Gelatinization temp score	4.13-7.00	6.09	6.84	1.27	0.64**
Panicles/hill	12-23	16	14	4.3	0.58**
Spikelet no./panicle	105-229	164	197	39	0.69**
% unfilled grains	9-26	15	14	10.2	0.25 ns
100-grain weight (g)	2.07-2.84	2.41	2.63	0.28	0.61**
Adjusted yield (g/2.25 m ²)	955-1893	1331	1690	460	0.47*

^aCorrelation between 26 pairs of S₁ and their derived S₄ lines. *, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Estimates of combining ability of some rice varieties in diallel crossing systems

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We studied the nature of genetic control and amount of heterosis available for spikelets per panicle and identified suitable donors for this character.

The rice genotypes crossed in a complete diallel set were IR8 (IRRI), IR8423 (IRRI), 415 (INSA), IR19746-11-33 (IRRI), VX1-2 (USSR), X1 (INSA), CICA7 (IRRI), Tam den HP (INSA), VE19, and Te hat to.

The 90 F₁ cross combinations and their parents were grown in a randomized block design with three replications in winter-spring 1986-87. Ten competitive randomly selected plants from each replication were analyzed.

Highly significant F ratios for general combining ability (GCA), specific combining ability (SCA), and reciprocal effects (Table 1) indicate difference among these effects. The GCA effects of each parent given in Table 2 indicate that IR8423-132-6-22, IR19746-11-33, and Tam den HP are good general combiners for number of spikelets/panicle.

For spikelets per panicle, the variances due to GCA were higher than those due to SCA for IR8423-132-6-22, X1, VE19, and Te hat to. This indicates the role of additive gene action was predominant in inheritance of the trait. In all entries

except X1, VE19, and Te hat to, nonadditive gene action was predominant in controlling this character. ■

Table 2. Estimate of GCA effects for spikelets/panicle.^a

Parent	GCA effects (gi)	Parent	GCA effects (gi)
IR8	5.57	x1	6.18
IR8423-132-6-22	12.75	CICA7	-8.54
415	-16.01	Tam den HP	10.65
IR19746-11-33	9.34	VE19	-9.69
VX1-2	6.54	Te hat to	-16.81

^aStandard error: gi - gj = 0.35 (i ≠ j).

Table 1. Analysis of variance of combining ability.

Source of variance ^a	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	Value	F-table P = 0.05
GCA	18908.00	9	2100.89	2122.11	2.53
SCA	11646.34	35	332.75	336.12	1.83
RE	6137.50	45	136.39	137.77	1.56
Error	0.99	171			

^aGCA = general combining ability, SCA = specific combining ability, RE = reciprocal effect.